

DESTINATION EARTH CO-DESIGN TOOLKIT

Worksheet 3.2

Operability Workshops

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Operability Workshop addresses how DestinE services can be realistically deployed and sustained in operational environments. It focuses on aligning technical feasibility with integration within the users' tools and processes, and long-term governance.

Structured around two modular blocks, Dataset and Infrastructure Review and Data Governance & Roadmap Validation, the workshop should be run either as a single extended session or divided into multiple meetings, depending on context and participant's profiles. It should bring together service providers, data providers, technical specialists, and user representatives to explore issues of data access, interoperability, security, and adoption. Exercises document technical requirements, identify bottlenecks, and clarify responsibilities for service continuity.

The workshop outputs a Data Management Plan and an agreed development roadmap that specify technical architectures, integration conditions, and governance mechanisms. By doing so, it bridges the gap between conceptual service design and practical deployment, ensuring that co-designed solutions are not only useful but also reliable, scalable, and resilient.

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1. Workshops focusing on Operability

1.1. Purpose and when to use this workshop

An operability co-design workshop shifts the focus from identifying what is useful to determining how it can actually be built and sustained within the technical and organizational environment of the platform. Its role is to transform prioritized user requirements or MVPs into actionable integration pathways by examining data availability, governance constraints, and the technical architecture needed for implementation. Design research shows that this phase often creates the risk of prematurely favoring what appears to be the most promising idea. Instead, operability work aims to secure a covering strategy: a set of generic integration decisions that can support several innovation pathways, accommodate different usage scenarios, and remain robust in the face of future evolution.

These workshops are most effective once the usefulness workshops have crystallized into a consensual specification sheet, and before major development resources are committed. At this stage, the conversation is less about imagination and more about feasibility. By systematically working through data needs, platform capacities, security requirements, and integration challenges, the workshop creates a shared understanding of what is possible, what gaps remain, and how those gaps can be mitigated.

The objective is to produce a realistic and transparent foundation for development: a Data Need-Matrix that highlights gaps and mitigation strategies, a first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) defining data and service lifecycle, and a set of integration decisions that anticipate technical and organizational constraints and take into account the broader ecosystem of users, partners, and potential collaborators involved in service delivery.

Another important dimension of operability is the identification of potential partners or stakeholders whose expertise or resources could strengthen service development. The workshop is an opportunity to explore who else should be involved to ensure sustainability and adoption.

Finally, operability discussions often generate a form of “retrofit” feedback to the platform itself: if data sets or tools identified as critical by users are not yet available within DestinE, the workshop outputs make these gaps visible so that the platform team can prioritize onboarding or integration. In this way, operability workshops not only prepare specific services for development, but also contribute to strengthening the platform ecosystem through integration choices that stay robust across different possible developments rather than relying on a single preferred option.

1.2. Participants and roles

Operability workshops bring together those who hold the technical and organisational levers of service implementation. Their configuration is **modular and adaptable**, depending on the objectives of the session and the stage of the process. Workshops can be conducted internally within the service development team, externally with partners and users, or in mixed formats involving representatives from DestinE/Serco and other stakeholders. This flexibility allows for a diversity of configurations to be mobilised according to needs.

- **Core participants** generally include the service providers’ team, responsible for designing the architecture and ensuring technical feasibility.
- **DestinE platform representatives** (e.g. Serco) may join when platform resources, integration, or governance constraints must be clarified.
- **Optional participants** can be invited depending on the workshop objectives:

- Data owners, providing input on licensing, access, quality, and coverage.
- Security and compliance specialists, ensuring privacy and adherence to standards.
- A power user, to validate usability and operability from an operational perspective.
- Identified partners, bringing complementary technical or organisational expertise.

2. Workshop preparation

2.1. Define purpose and goals

Preparation for an operability workshop is as much about providing the right material as it is about aligning expectations. Unlike the usefulness workshops, where participants arrive with their lived experience, operability workshops depend on technical artefacts that must be ready for discussion. These include a draft Data Need-Matrix, outlining the datasets linked to the prioritized requirements, and a draft Data Management Plan (DMP) that proposes how data governance, access, and lifecycle might be organized. Sharing these documents in advance ensures participants do not start from a blank page but rather focus their effort on refining, questioning, and validating the content.

WHAT TO DO DURING THE PURPOSE DEFINITION STAGE:

- **Share the consensual specification sheet** from the usefulness workshops to remind participants of the agreed priorities.
- **If needed, circulate a draft Data Need-Matrix** linked to the prioritised requirements.
- Prepare and share a draft Data Management Plan (DMP).
- **Assign clear roles:** facilitator, technical recorder, note-taker.
- **Test the physical or digital environment** in advance to ensure smooth documentation and collaboration.

2.2. Identify data and infrastructure

A critical step before the operability workshop is to map the technical landscape in which the service will operate. This requires exploring both the data already available within the DestinE platform and the infrastructure that supports it. Service providers and platform representatives should compile a preliminary list of datasets accessible through DestinE, noting their formats, space and time coverage, access protocols, update cycles, and any usage or licensing constraints. This inventory should then be compared against the prioritized requirements from the consensual specification sheet, highlighting which datasets are already in place, which may need to be onboarded.

In parallel, it is important to document the infrastructure dependencies that will influence feasibility. These include runtime environments, APIs, computational capacity, storage, authentication systems, and interoperability arrangements with external tools and workflows. Anticipating these dependencies allows the workshop to focus on realistic options and prepares participants to engage in informed trade-off discussions.

Equally important is to consider user perspectives on integration challenges. During the usefulness workshops, participants may already have raised concerns about how a future service would fit into their daily environment—whether linked to IT policies, existing software, workflows, or organizational practices. Capturing these insights before the operability workshop ensures that technical mapping is grounded not only in platform capabilities but also in the realities of adoption on the user side.

This preparatory work ensures that participants enter the workshop with a clear picture of the technical baseline. It provides the necessary foundation for identifying integration challenges, deciding how to handle gaps, and ensuring that the services envisioned are not only useful but also buildable within the constraints of the platform.

WHAT TO DO DURING THE DATA AND INFRASTRUCTURE IDENTIFICATION STAGE:

- **Compile a list of available datasets** within the DestinE platform.
- **Note dataset characteristics** (formats, space and time coverage, access protocols, update cycles, constraints).
- **Compare the dataset inventory against the specification sheet** to highlight gaps.
- **Map infrastructure dependencies** (APIs, runtimes, storage, authentication, interoperability).
- **Review user feedback** on integration challenges from previous workshops and include it in the preparatory material.
- **Prepare a concise overview document** for participants to review before the session.

2.3. Design the agenda

An operability workshop needs a clear and structured agenda that balances technical exploration with decision-making. The session should follow a sequence that makes it possible to assess dataset availability, explore integration constraints, draft management practices, and converge toward a feasible implementation pathway.

The agenda should begin with a framing segment that recalls the consensual specification sheet and clarifies the objectives of this workshop cycle. Participants must be reminded that the focus at this stage is feasibility: assessing which requirements can be met with existing resources, which require negotiation with the platform, and which may involve new development or external partnerships.

The central part of the agenda can be organized around two exercises:

- **Dataset and infrastructure review**, using the Data Need-Matrix to test availability and highlight gaps.
- **Data governance and sustainability management**, initiated through the draft Data Management Plan (DMP).

When the workshop involves both service providers and external users, subgroup work is recommended. Alternating between plenary discussions and smaller subgroup exchanges allows diverse expertise to surface and provides space for both technical and organizational perspectives. Each cycle should allow time for individual reflection, group discussion, and plenary exchange.

If the workshop is conducted by the service providers team alone, the agenda can be simplified to a plenary format. In this case, the focus should be on structured time blocks dedicated to each of the technical building blocks, ensuring that discussions remain concentrated and decisions are reached efficiently without the need for subgroup work.

The session should end with a synthesis segment where the facilitator presents the main points of convergence, highlights remaining gaps, and secures agreement on next steps. This ensures that participants leave with a shared understanding of the outcomes and a clear view of the way forward.

WHAT TO DO DURING THE DESIGN OF AGENDAS STAGE:

The agenda of an operability workshop should be built around the specific technical questions that need to be clarified rather than systematically mobilizing all available tools. Its design must remain flexible and tailored to the workshop's objectives and participants.

- **Open with a framing introduction that recalls the consensual specification sheet,** restates the goals of the workshop, and presents the structured agenda. This helps align participants and ensures everyone understands the technical issues at stake.
- **Address technical points progressively.** For example: 1 / Problem 1 (e.g. dataset availability or licensing), 2 / Problem 2 (e.g. integration with existing infrastructure), 3 / Problem 3 (e.g. performance or security constraints).
- **For each point, combine focused discussions and exchanges between the relevant experts.** Alternate between subgroup work and plenary discussions if both users and providers are present; use a plenary-only format if the session is internal to the development team.
- **Synthesize findings** by recapping the main insights and agreements reached for each technical point.
- **Conclude with a working model or action plan,** assigning responsibilities, setting next steps, and outlining the roadmap for technical integration.
- **Share the agenda in advance with all participants** to align expectations and allow preparation.

2.4. Workshop setup

Templates, canvases, and worksheets of the co-design toolkit provide a structure that allow ideas to be originated and captured in a form that can be 'synthesized later. To support the conversation, GIS maps, service mock-ups, or data visualisations help participants anchor their conversation into tangible realizations. As for any state-of-art workshop, facilitation roles should be clarified (facilitators, notetakers); logistics should be considered (e.g. internet speed, room layout, lighting, accessibility, remote connections), and knowledge capture methods should be secured (e.g. photos, digital boards, recordings).

3. Key exercises for operability workshops

The operability workshop is conceived as a flexible process that can be structured around one or several core building blocks, such as Dataset and Infrastructure Review or Data Governance & Roadmap Validation. Depending on the objectives, context, and availability of participants, these blocks can be addressed in a single extended session or distributed across multiple workshops. The modular design allows facilitators to adapt the agenda to very specific technical questions while maintaining methodological coherence and ensuring that each point is treated in depth.

3.1. Exercises for dataset & infrastructure review

This block translates the consensual specification sheet into concrete assumptions about which datasets and technological bricks are required and how they can be mobilised on DestinE. The aim is to build a shared, realistic picture of what is already available, what must be adapted or onboarded, and what is missing. Beyond listing data, the review also looks at infrastructure dependencies (APIs, runtimes, storage, authentication, interoperability with GIS and other tools) and captures early "retrofit" signals for the platform when high-value datasets or services are absent. The outcome is a consolidated, decision-ready Data-Use-Need Matrix and an initial feasibility map per requirement (see worksheet 3.4 – Data-Use-Need matrix).

Core modular exercise available here:

- **Data-Use-Need Matrix** (per requirement: datasets & variables, resolution/latency/volume, licensing & access, “available on DestinE?”, quality/coverage, gap & mitigation, owner/next action). *For detailed instructions on how to use the Data-Need Matrix, please refer to the worksheet 3.4.*

	Thème 1 Légitimer l'arrosage des parcs en cas d'avis de sécheresse	Thème 2 Le référencement participatif des arbres de la ville	Thème 3 Assistance au pilotage pour la sécurité des parcs et jardin	Thème 4 « Le bon arbre au bon endroit »	Thème 5 Suivi et mesure de l'impact de la canopée végétale
Brique 3	X	X	X	X	X
Brique 6	X	X	X	X	X
Brique 2	X	X	X		
Brique 4			X	X	X
Brique 1	X				
Brique 5	X				X
...		X			X
Brique n		X			X

Brique existant en interne

Brique existante en externe propriétaire

Brique existante en open source

connaissance scientifique disponible mais brique non développée

Gap scientifique

	Thème 1 Légitimer l'arrosage des parcs en cas d'avis de sécheresse	Thème 2 Le référencement participatif des arbres de la ville	Thème 3 Assistance au pilotage pour la sécurité des parcs et jardin	Thème 4 « Le bon arbre au bon endroit »	Thème 5 Suivi et mesure de l'impact de la canopée végétale
Brique 3	X	X	X	X	X
Brique 6	X	X	X	X	X
Brique 2	X	X	X	X	X
Brique 4			X	X	X
Brique 1	X				
Brique 5	X				X
...		X			X
Brique n		X			X

Brique existant en interne

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Gap scientifique

WHAT TO DO DURING DATASET & INFRASTRUCTURE REVIEW EXERCISES:

- **Open and anchor the task:** Reconnect to the consensual specification sheet and make explicit the evaluation lens: feasibility today, feasible with adaptation, or not feasible yet. State the decision criteria you will use (availability, quality/coverage, licensing/access, integration effort, cost/performance risks).
- **Run the facilitation cycle if needed:**
 - ⇒ *Individual work* – each participant marks the matrix for their requirement(s): propose datasets, note availability/licensing, flag known gaps.
 - ⇒ *Sub-group discussion* – compare entries, remove duplicates, add missing sources, and qualify quality/coverage and latency needs; begin listing mitigations (onboard, substitute, preprocess, cache).
 - ⇒ *Plenary exchange* – each group presents its top confirmations, biggest gaps, and proposed mitigations; align on colour-coding (green/amber/red) per requirement.
- **Guide the review step by step:** Start with data (what exists where; who owns it; under which license; expected cadence), then move to infrastructure (which runtime, API endpoints, packaging, formats, storage, authentication; links to downstream tools such as GIS). Keep discussions concrete by asking for examples and, when possible, checking a sample file or endpoint.
- **Document live in the matrix:** Fill the Data Need-Matrix on screen; add columns as needed for “Gap & mitigation” and “Owner / next action / ETA”. Capture assumptions and open questions verbatim so they can be verified after the session.
- **Converge before closing:** consolidate a shared portfolio of feasible options by summarizing the data and infrastructure status for each requirement (green/amber/red), listing retrofit requests to DestinE (high-value missing datasets or platform features), and identifying potential partners for specific components. Confirm who will validate licensing, who will test a sample, and who will draft the first DMP entries for each requirement.

3.2. Exercises for governance and roadmap validation through the DMP sheet

The third block focuses on consolidating the technical and organizational insights gathered so far into a structured Data Management Plan (DMP). This stage is about moving from fragmented inputs (datasets, infrastructures, integration challenges) to a coherent governance framework that ensures a resulting sustainable service aligned with FAIR (Findable,

Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles. The DMP is not just an administrative requirement but a living instrument that defines how data are handled across their full lifecycle, how responsibilities are distributed, and how services will remain viable in the long term.

In the context of DestinE, the DMP builds on the Horizon Europe model, extended with dimensions on sustainability, resource allocation, ethics, and security. Its role is to connect technical feasibility with governance: linking the datasets and infrastructures identified in the previous workshops with concrete provisions for data and metadata, accessibility, interoperability, and re-use, while also ensuring that security, ethics, and long-term preservation are addressed.

Core modular exercise available here:

- **Drafting or refining the Data Management Plan** using the DestinE co-design templates, with specific attention to:
 - Data summary (origin, type, format, utility, expected size).
 - FAIR principles (findability through metadata, accessibility through trusted repositories, interoperability through standards, re-usability through licenses and documentation).
 - Sustainability and governance (allocation of resources, data security, ethics, ownership, roles and responsibilities).
 - Integration into the DestinE platform and alignment with the DESP's role as a gateway for policy-relevant data services.

For detailed instructions on how to use the DMP, please refer to the worksheet 3.5.

WHAT TO DO DURING THE GOVERNANCE AND ROADMAP VALIDATION EXERCISE:

- **Draft Frame the objective:** Remind participants that the purpose of this block is to validate and enrich the DMP, ensuring that all technical and organisational dimensions are covered. Stress that this is where integration into the broader DestinE framework is anchored.
- **Structure group work:** Depending on the number of participants, form sub-groups around the main DMP dimensions. For example, one group could work on FAIR principles (metadata, data, repositories, interoperability), another on governance and sustainability (roles, responsibilities, resources), and another on adoption and ethics.
- **Apply the facilitation cycle (see previous sections).**
- **Encourage concrete references:** Ask participants to connect their inputs with existing practices or examples (for instance, data and metadata standards they already use, trusted repositories, or organisational procedures for data security).
- **Document in real time:** Use the DMP template to capture validated inputs directly. Show participants how their contributions populate the DMP draft. This reinforces ownership and transparency.
- **Manage dynamics:** Keep discussions grounded in feasibility, avoid drifting into abstract ideals. If disagreements emerge (e.g., on data access levels), record them and flag them for resolution at governance level rather than forcing consensus prematurely.
- **Converge before closing:** Summarise the validated elements of the DMP, highlight any outstanding gaps or decisions, and agree on who will finalise the document.

Confirm that the DMP will serve as the foundation for the service roadmap and adoption strategy.

4. Workshop synthesis and follow-up

What happens in the immediate aftermath of the workshops determines whether the technical and organizational discussions are transformed into actionable next steps for service development. Raw contributions must be cleaned, consolidated, and made usable; participants need to see that their expertise has been valued; and the decisions taken must be made visible to sustain momentum. Skipping or delaying this phase risks losing technical precision, eroding trust, and weakening the collective ownership of the roadmap.

4.1. Synthesize outputs and share outcomes

The first task is to transform the diverse workshop materials (Data Need-Matrix entries, Integration Challenges templates, DMP drafts, notes, and verbal inputs) into a coherent synthesis. This synthesis should be both technically precise and accessible, balancing fidelity to participants' contributions with clarity of presentation.

- **From raw data to structured outputs:** Write up the consolidated Data Need-Matrix, specifying which datasets are available, which require adaptation, and which are missing. Summarize the integration challenges raised, grouping them into technical, organisational, and adoption categories, and indicate proposed mitigations. For the DMP, highlight the validated elements of FAIR data management, governance, and sustainability.
- **Filling the outcomes diagram:** The main results of the workshop should be mapped onto the outcomes diagram (see *Worksheet 4*). This step transforms fragmented insights into a shared visual synthesis, showing how the various ideas, service concepts, and collaboration opportunities relate to short-, mid-, and long-term perspectives. Updating the diagram after each workshop helps establish a continuous thread between sessions and creates a basis for discussion at the beginning of the next phase.
- **Traceability and transparency:** Link findings back to original templates or direct participant contributions whenever possible. This makes the synthesis recognizable and builds trust in the process.
- **Timely communication:** Share a concise summary within a few days. It should restate the objectives of the workshop, highlight the main conclusions, and present the agreed roadmap. Supporting visuals such as screenshots of the Data Need-Matrix or annotated Integration Challenges templates help to convey the technical substance while keeping the narrative accessible.
- **Two-way validation:** Circulate the synthesis not as a final report but as a draft for comment. Invite corrections, clarifications, and additions. This ensures technical accuracy and reinforces the sense of shared responsibility.

4.2. Evaluate and capture learning

Workshops are also opportunities to refine the co-design process itself. Evaluation should be both external (from participants) and internal (from facilitators).

- **Participant feedback:** Ask for short reflections, either in a closing round or via a quick survey on what worked, what was unclear, and what could be improved.
- **Facilitator reflection:** Debrief as a team, considering agenda pacing, group dynamics, effectiveness of exercises, and quality of captured outputs. Documenting these lessons builds organizational capacity and ensures that each subsequent workshop improves.

- **Quality check:** Before finalizing synthesis, verify that the outputs meet the intended objectives of the workshop stage (e.g., identification of needs, refinement into requirements, consensus validation).

4.3. Sustain engagement and build continuity

The period after an operability workshop is critical to maintain alignment between users, service providers, and platform representatives. Engagement must continue beyond the session to preserve momentum and confidence.

BEST PRACTICES TO SUSTAIN ENGAGEMENT AND BUILD CONTINUITY

- **Frame Keep participants in the loop:** Provide regular updates on their contributions shaping the design process. This can include newsletters, short progress emails, or prototypes previews.
- **Plan follow-ups:** If gaps or unresolved questions remain, schedule additional workshops or smaller check-ins.
- **Engage participants in the development cycle:** Where possible, involve users not only in ideation but also in testing and iteration of prototypes.
- **Celebrate contributions:** Acknowledge participants' time and expertise, whether through formal recognition in reports, informal thank-you notes, or shared authorship of insights.

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